

Synthesis and study of new mesogenic homologous series : 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes

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Abstract : A new homologous series of liquid crystals viz. 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes comprising eleven mesogens have been synthesized. The first four members of the series are non-mesogenic while nematic mesophase commences from fifth member of the series. Polymesomorphism occurs in eighth, tenth and twelfth member of the series. Only smectic mesophase occurs in fourteenth and sixteenth member of the series. The usual odd-even effect is observed in nematic-isotropic transition curve. The smectic-isotropic transition curve rises and falls smoothly as the series is ascended in usual manner. The mesomorphic range is wide. The thermal stability and mesomorphic characteristic are compared with structurally similar homologous series. Analytical data support the structure of molecules. It is middle ordered melting type with threaded texture of nematic phase and focal conic fan shaped texture of smectic mesophase.

Keywords : Liquid crystal, mesogens, mesomorphism, nematic, smectic.

A new homologous series with two central bridges -COO- and -N=N- and common core structure except varying terminal group is synthesized. Present work was planned to synthesize new liquid crystal material and relation of varying terminal groups with mesogenic characteristics.

Experimental

Homologues of the homologous series were prepared as under :

- (1) Synthesis of 4-alkoxy benzoic acid from *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid was carried out by known method¹.
- (2) Synthesis of 4-hydroxy naphthylazo-4'-acetylbenzene was carried out by treating *p*-aminoacetophenone through diazotization with α -naphthol by usual method².
- (3) 4-*n*-Alkoxy benzoic acids were converted to 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chlorides² by refluxing with freshly distilled thionyl chloride and acid chloride so obtained were directly condensed with 4-hydroxy naphthylazo-4'-acetylbenzene in pyridine after removal of excess thionyl chloride. Products were purified and recrystallised from alcohol.

The transition temperatures of the homologue of the homologous series are observed through a Laborlux po-

larizing microscope provided with heating stage. Analytical data (Table 2) confirms the structure of the homologues.

Results and discussion

The transition temperature of all the eleven homologues are reported in Table 1. It shows that first four members are nonmesomorphic in nature while mesomorphism commences from the fifth homologue to the last homologue. The fifth and sixth members are enantiotropic nematic while eighth, tenth and twelfth homologues are polymesomorphic possessing smectic and nematic character. The last two homologue of the series i.e. fourteenth and sixteenth members are enantiotropic smectic with disappearance of nematic mesophase. Transition temperatures are plotted versus the number of carbon atoms of *n*-alkyl chain of *n*-alkoxy group and phase diagram is obtained as shown in Fig. 1, from Table 1.

The solid-isotropic or solid-mesomorphic transition curve follows partly a zig-zag path of rising and falling as series is ascended. The nematic-isotropic transition curve initially rises and then smoothly fall as series is ascended from fifth to the last member of the series. The usual odd-even effect is observed in nematic-isotropic

Table 1. Transition temperatures of the homologous series :
4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzyloxy)-naphthylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes

Sl. no.	R = <i>n</i> -Alkyl group	Transition temp. (°C)		
		Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
1.	Methyl	-	-	185.0
2.	Ethyl	-	-	178.0
3.	Propyl	-	-	169.0
4.	Butyl	-	-	161.0
5.	Pentyl	-	128.0	155.0
6.	Hexyl	-	139.0	182.0
7.	Octyl	93.0	141.0	168.0
8.	Decyl	113.0	147.0	166.0
9.	Dodecyl	94.0	145.0	153.0
10.	Tetradecyl	87.0	-	138.0
11.	Hexadecyl	71.0	-	120.0

transition curve³. The smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic transition curve rises and falls smoothly as the series is ascended in usual manner. The smectic-nematic transition curve is extrapolated to seventh member of the series, so as to determine the latent transition temperature for smectic and it is 130.0 °C. The texture of the nematic mesophase is threaded type while that of the smectic mesophase are focal conic fan shaped of the smectic of the type A or C as judged directly by visualizing the field of view of polarizing microscope.

The mesomorphic characteristics of the title homologous series (1) is compared with geometrically identical homologous series (A) and (B).

The homologous series (1), (A) and (B) contain common core structure like three phenyl rings bridged through -COO- and -N=N- group and common left *n*-alkoxy terminal group. The middle phenyl ring fused with other phenyl ring (i.e. naphthyl ring). They differ only by functional group or groups substituted on third right handed

Fig. 1. Phase transition diagram for 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzyloxy)-naphthylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes.

Table 2. Elemental analysis

Sr. no.	R = <i>n</i> -Alkyl chain	Molecular formula	Calcd. (%) N	Obsd. (%) N
1.	Methyl	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	6.60	6.59
2.	Ethyl	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	6.39	6.01
3.	Propyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	6.19	6.38
4.	Butyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	6.00	5.87
5.	Pentyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₄	5.83	5.78
6.	Hexyl	C ₃₁ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₄	5.67	5.73
7.	Octyl	C ₃₃ H ₃₄ N ₂ O ₄	5.36	5.53
8.	Decyl	C ₃₅ H ₃₈ N ₂ O ₄	5.09	5.15
9.	Dodecyl	C ₃₇ H ₄₂ N ₂ O ₄	4.84	4.30
10.	Tetradecyl	C ₃₉ H ₄₆ N ₂ O ₄	4.62	4.78
11.	Hexadecyl	C ₄₁ H ₅₀ N ₂ O ₄	4.42	4.39

¹H NMR : 4-(4'-*n*-Decylkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes : (200 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) 1.28 (-CH₂-CH₂ of -C₁₀H₂₁), 2.61 (-CH₃ of -CH₃-CO), 1.84 (-OCH₂-CH₂ of -OC₁₀H₂₁), 4.09 (-OCH₂ of -OCH₂-C₅H₁₀), 8.99 and 8.31, 6.90 and 7.03 (two *p*-sub. benzene rings).

¹H NMR : 4-(4'-*n*-Tetradecylkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes : (200 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) : 1.26 (*t*-CH₂-CH₂ of -C₁₄H₂₉), 2.69 (-CH₃ of -CH₃-CO), 4.118 (-OCH₂ of -OCH₂-C₁₃H₂₇), 8.99 and 8.266, 7.024 and 6.933 (two *p*-sub. benzene rings).

phenyl ring. Thus variation in liquid crystallinity and degree of liquid crystallinity exhibited can be assigned due to replacement of varying functional end groups like -COCH₃, -Cl and 2,5-dichloro groups⁵. First four non-mesomorphic homologues have relatively shorter *n*-alkoxy chain length while remaining mesogenic members of the series have relatively longer alkoxy chain. A homologue with shorter chain length undergo stronger intermolecular forces of attractions and hence possess high crystallinity while a homologue with longer chain length experience relatively weaker intermolecular forces of attraction inducing amorphous character in a sample of the substance i.e. crystallinity character is diminished to such an extent that, a sample of the substance maintain two dimensional order of array of molecules in floating condition. This results into exhibition of liquid crystalline state/mesogenic state of a substance on heating while, a sample of a substance with high crystallinity directly passes into isotropic liquid from solid without exhibition of an intermediate state of substance called mesomorphic state. Thus first five homologues are nonmesomorphic and remaining members of the series are mesomorphic. As series is ascended, the amorphous character in a sample substance predominates, which maintain high or low degree ordered arrangement of molecules in floating condi-

(1) 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes(B) 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-4''-chlorobenzenes⁴**Fig. 2**

tion giving rise to occurrence of either nematic and/or smectic mesophase⁶. Odd-even effect observed in nematic-isotropic transition curve and alternation of transition temperatures in solid-isotropic or solid-mesomorphic transition curve are attributed to the presence of odd-even methylene units in the *n*-alkoxy chain of left alkoxy terminal. Mesomorphic range is relatively high and series is of middle ordered melting type. Thus series is partly smectogenic and partly nematogenic. Normally the substances with naphthyl ring are nematogenic but title homologous series is partly smectogenic. This suggests that highly polar acetyl end group causes stronger intermolecular forces of attractions as compared to -Cl and dichloro end groups. The relative thermal stabilities of series under discussion i.e. series (1), (A) and (B) are recorded in Table 3 as under.

Table 3. Relative thermal stabilities

Series →	Relative thermal stabilities in °C		
	(1)	(A)	(B)
Smectic-isotropic or smectic-nematic	138.2	-	-
Commencement of smectic phase	C ₈ -C ₁₆	-	-
Nematic-isotropic or isotropic-nematic	164.8	129.5	121.9
Commencement of nematic phase	C ₅	C ₅	C ₃

The nematic-isotropic or isotropic-nematic thermal stabilities are in decreasing order from series (1) → (A) → (B). Width of the molecule is more in case of series (A) as compared to series (1) and (B) i.e. 2,5-dichloro substitution. The -COCH₃ group being more polar than -Cl group positioned at *para* position in series (1) and (B) respectively causes stronger intermolecular forces of at-

tractions. Thus higher polarity and polarizability of $-\text{COCH}_3$ terminal group induces higher thermal stability than series (B) irrespective of their identical length to breadth ratio. But presence of two $-\text{Cl}$ groups linked to third phenyl ring i.e. 2,5-dichloro group in which length to breadth ratio decreases as compared to series (1) and (B). However increased width of the molecule, increases polarizability of the molecule. Thus increased polarizability of 2,5-dichloro derivatives induces stronger intermolecular forces of attractions than series (B) but cannot surpass the magnitude of intermolecular forces of attractions amongst the molecules of series (1) under present discussion, i.e. thermal stability of series (A) for nematic mesophase is more than series (B) but it is less than series (1). Moreover stronger intermolecular attraction due to higher polarity of $-\text{COCH}_3$ stabilizes exhibition of smectic mesophase while it does not appear in case of $-\text{Cl}$ and 2,5-dichloro derivatives. Thus though naphthyl derivatives are generally nematogenic but smectogenic character may be induced by substituting highly polar groups like $-\text{COCH}_3$. Commencement of nematic character takes place early i.e. from third member of the series (B) but it occurs from fifth member of series (1) and (A). Thus group efficiency order derived for nematic on the basis of thermal stability is,

Conclusion :

A new homologous azoester series is synthesized. It is partly smectogenic and partly nematogenic with middle ordered melting type. Group efficiency order derived for

nematic mesophase formation is,

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